

Revisiting the Tisserand Parameter as a Proxy for Asteroid Stability in N -body Simulations

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Abstract

This study investigates whether short-term variability in the Tisserand parameter T_J can serve as a fast and computationally efficient proxy for long-term orbital stability in the main asteroid belt using the T_J defined with respect to Jupiter as the perturbing body. A sample of 66 asteroids spanning key dynamical regions was analysed using short-term observational data from NASA JPL Horizons and long-term numerical integrations performed with the REBOUND N -body framework. The time-dependent Tisserand parameter and its first-order sensitivity with respect to semi-major axis were evaluated and compared using a symmetric relative error metric.

The results show mean discrepancies of 7.96% in $T_J(t)$ and 9.3% in its semi-major axis sensitivity ($\frac{\partial T_J}{\partial a}|_t$), indicating reasonable agreement between short- and long-term dynamical behaviour. Weak correlations between error metrics suggest that the two quantities capture distinct aspects of orbital evolution, while increasing deviations toward the outer belt are consistent with longer-timescale perturbative effects.

These findings suggest that the Tisserand parameter, when treated as a time-dependent quantity, can provide a useful first-order screening tool for asteroid stability, potentially reducing reliance on computationally expensive long-term integrations during early-stage dynamical analysis.

Introduction

The Tisserand Parameter (T_J) is traditionally used as a classification tool in celestial mechanics, distinguishing dynamical populations relative to Jupiter. In the CR3BP, T_J is approximately conserved and therefore acts as a quasi-invariant.

Despite this property, its application as an active dynamical diagnostic in N -body simulations remains limited. Most stability analyses rely on computationally expensive long-term integrations or chaos indicators such as Lyapunov exponents.

Methodology

A sample of 66 asteroids was selected across seven orbital regions defined by semi-major axis boundaries:

- Hungaria Group (1.78–2.00 AU)
- Transitional Zone (2.00–2.06 AU)
- Inner Main Belt (2.06–2.50 AU)
- Middle Main Belt (2.50–2.82 AU)
- 5:2–7:3 Region (2.82–2.96 AU)
- Outer Main Belt (2.96–3.28 AU)
- Cybele Group (3.28–3.70 AU)

Two datasets were compared:

- **JPL Horizons:** 1-year observational data (1-hour timestep)
- **REBOUND:** 1 Myr N -body integration (Wisdom-Holman integrator)

Symmetric relative error is defined as:

$$\text{Error} = \frac{|X_{JPL} - X_{REB}|}{(X_{JPL} + X_{REB})/2} \times 100\%$$

Time-dependent Tisserand Parameter and Its First-Order Sensitivity

$$T_J(t) = \frac{a_J(t)}{a(t)} + 2\sqrt{\frac{a(t)}{a_J(t)}(1 - e(t)^2)\cos i(t)} \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial T_J}{\partial a}|_t = -\frac{a_J(t)}{a(t)^2} + \sqrt{\frac{1 - e(t)^2}{a(t) \cdot a_J(t)}} \cos i(t) \quad (2)$$

where $a(t)$, $e(t)$, and $i(t)$ are the asteroid's instantaneous semi-major axis, eccentricity, and inclination respectively, and $a_J(t)$ is Jupiter's semi-major axis as a function of time.

Results

Figure 1. Corner plot showing the pairwise relationship between the average semi-major axis and the mean Tisserand parameter $T_J(t)$ comparing JPL Horizons (blue) and REBOUND (orange) datasets showing the marginal distributions of each variable, while the off-diagonal panel shows their joint distribution.

Figure 1 presents a corner plot comparing the semi-major axis and mean $T_J(t)$ distributions between both datasets. They recover the expected negative correlation between semi-major axis and $T_J(t)$, confirming that asteroids at greater heliocentric distances are consistent with reduced short-term sensitivity to perturbation effects relative to Jupiter. However, the REBOUND population has slightly smaller semi-major axes relative to the JPL dataset, reflecting the possible cumulative effect of Jovian perturbations eroding T_J over the 1 Myr integration timescale. The marginal histograms further illustrate that while the semi-major axis distributions remain broadly consistent between the two methods.

Figure 2. Tisserand parameter variations from the JPL Horizons (Cross) and REBOUND (Circle) as a function of the semi-major axis. Both datasets follow the $\frac{1}{a}$ dependence, with strong correlations of $r = 0.926$ and $r = 0.953$ respectively.

Figure 3. Relative error in T_J as a function of the average semi-major axis

As shown in Figure 3, across both datasets for 66 asteroids spanning seven orbital families, a weak negative correlation indicates that asteroids at greater heliocentric distances tend to exhibit smaller T_J errors between the short- and long-term datasets, consistent with reduced short-term sensitivity due to the perturbation gradients relative to Jupiter.

Figure 4. Relative error in $\frac{\partial T_J}{\partial a}|_t$ as a function of the average semi-major axis

Through this, a moderate positive correlation indicates that asteroids at greater heliocentric distances tend to exhibit larger gradient errors between the short- and long-term datasets, suggesting that $\frac{\partial T_J}{\partial a}|_t$ becomes difficult to recover from short-term data in the outer belt region. Two Cybele asteroids are found having 40% error, and this shows the longer dynamical timescales characteristic of that population.

Discussion

The mean errors of 7.96% in $T_J(t)$ and 9.3% in $\frac{\partial T_J}{\partial a}|_t$ indicate reasonable agreement between short- and long-term datasets despite their difference in timescale, supporting the use of short-term T_J variability as a preliminary stability screening tool.

Two sources contribute to the reported errors: the difference in integration timescale (1 year vs 1 Myr) and the difference in model complexity (full JPL N -body vs reduced $N = 7$ REBOUND system). Both contribute systematically and cannot be fully disentangled in the current setup.

The increasing $\frac{\partial T_J}{\partial a}|_t$ errors toward the outer belt reflect longer dynamical timescales in that region, where one year of data is insufficient to fully resolve the perturbation signal. The weak correlation ($r = 0.17$) between the two error metrics confirms that $T_J(t)$ and its gradient capture complementary dynamical information rather than redundant signals.

Asteroids showing classification mismatches between JPL and REBOUND also tend to exhibit elevated short-term errors, suggesting that T_J variability can flag dynamically active bodies for follow-up long-term analysis.

Conclusion

- Short-term $T_J(t)$ variability derived from 1 year of JPL Horizons data shows reasonable agreement with 1 Myr REBOUND integrations, with mean errors of 7.96% and 9.3% for $T_J(t)$ and $\frac{\partial T_J}{\partial a}|_t$ respectively.
- The Tisserand parameter, when treated as a time-dependent diagnostic rather than a static classifier, provides a computationally efficient first-order screening tool for asteroid stability without requiring expensive long-term integrations. Classification mismatches and elevated errors identify dynamically active bodies suitable for targeted follow-up analysis.
- Future work will expand the sample, incorporate inclination-based family discrimination, and validate against Lyapunov exponents and frequency map analysis.

Acknowledgement

We would like to thank Hanno Rein (University of Toronto) and Daniel Tamayo (Harvey Mudd College) for their advice and encouragement to conduct this study.

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